

A study on Services of Tech Mahindra

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Abstract

Tech Mahindra limited Business method Outsourcing is an Indian multinational provider of information technologies(IT), networking technology solution and Business process outsourcing (BPO) to numerous trade verticals and horizontals. Anand mahindra is the Chairman of tech Mahindra, which is headquartered is at Pune and has its registered workplace in Mumbai. Part of the Mahindra Group, Tech Mahindra is an US\$4.7 billion company with over 113,550 employees in 90 countries Tech Mahindra was ranked 5th in India's software services firms and overall 111th in Fortune india's five hundred list for 2012. Tech Mahindra, on 25th June 2013, announced the completion of merger with Mahindra Satyam. Mahindra & Mahindra started venture with British telecom in 1986 as technology outsourcing firm. British telecom initially had around 30 % stake within the tech Mahindra company. In december 2010, British telecom sold five.5 per cent of its stake in Tech Mahindra to Mahindra & Mahindra for Rs 451 crores. In Aug 2012, British Telecom sold 14.1 per cent of its stake to institutional investors for about Rs 1,395 crores. In Dec 2012, British Telecom sold its remaining 9.1 per cent (11.6 million share) shareholding to institutional investors for a total gross cash proceeds of Rs 1,011.4 crores. This sales marked the exit of British telecom from tech Mahindra. Tech Mahindra declared its merger with the Mahindra Satyam on March twenty one, 2012, after the boards of the two companies gave their approval, to create 2.5 billion \$ IT Companys. The two corporations had received the go-ahead for the merger from bombay stock exchange and therefore the National stock exchange. On June 11th, 2013, andhra pradesh state supreme court gave its approval for the merger of Mahindra Satyam with tech Mahindra, once the bombay state supreme court had already given its approval to Tech Mahindra got the approval from the registrar of companies for the merger at 11:45 pm on June 24th, 2013. Jul 5, 2013 has been determined as the record date on that the Satyam computer Services ('Mahindra Satyam') shares are swapped for tech Mahindra shares underneath the approved theme. Mahindra Satyam, was suspended from trading with effect from Jul 4th, 2013, following the merger. Tech Mahindra completed shares swap and allocated its shares to the shareholders of Mahindra Satyam on Jul 12th, 2013. The stock exchanges have accorded their approval for trading the new shares effective July 12, 2013. Tech Mahindra posted net profit of Rs 686 crores for the first quarter ended June 30th, 2013, up 27% compared to the corresponding quarter last year.

Keywords: Tech Mahindra, Anand mahindra, National Stock Exchange, Mahindra Satyam

1. INTRODUCTION

Tech Mahindra began as a joint venture with British Telecom and the company began as Mahindra-British Telecom in the year 1986. This was the time when the IT revolution was unthinkable. For a company that was into the manufacturing of automobile and the steel, its foray into telecom and IT was a tactical move to diversify the Mahindra Group. TCS, Infosys and WIPRO were headed to the success in 80s, and Mahindra Group's step was a clear quest in search for new opportunities.

By 1995, it had established office in UK and expanded to Germany in 2001. Till then, Mahindra-BT was more into telecom software. It was an acquisition of Axes Technologies that really made the company takeoff. By 2005, Mahindra-BT was eighth largest software exporter in India. The name was changed to Tech Mahindra in the year 2006. After clearing the roadblocks, Mahindra headed to the best strategy ever. The acquisition of Satyam Computers in 2009 made Tech Mahindra become a player in the Indian IT industry. Satyam Computer's was rocked by a financial crisis and hit an all-time low. Mahindra jumped at the opportunity.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To know the Accenture Partners and Alliances.
- To analyse the HR strategies of Accenture.
- To analyse the company using SWOT analysis.
- To analyse the achievements and the growth of the company.
- To analyse the environmental strategy of Accenture.
- To analyse the services and solutions provided by the Accenture.
- To know the leadership team at Accenture.
- To find the competitors of Accenture.

3. SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

IT Services: Leveraging industry expertise, technology insight and outsourcing capabilities, we provide end-to-end services and solutions to our customers: from idea to delivery, from change intent to transformation.

We have customized our Information Technology services for utilities customers around our core service offerings:

- Enterprise Business Solutions
- Enterprise Asset Management
- Content Management and Web Portal Development
- Business Intelligence and Analytics

- Application development and Management
- Infrastructure Management
- Business process outsourcing and Knowledge process outsourcing
- Integrated Engineering Services
- Consulting Services

Integrated Technology Solutions for Business Transformation: Business transformation helps companies align their technology initiatives with their business strategy and vision. Our Business Transformation solution provides business consulting, information technology re-engineering and application integration, business processes alignment and real-time management; thereby enabling companies to respond to changing market dynamics.

Integrating information technology with operational technologies has become far more important for ensuring a successful transformation. So, we have partnered with leading utilities and technology companies to create frameworks and adopters for integrating business and information technology quickly with minimum investment and risk.

Our belief that information technology should be driven by the domain has helped us in identifying the right challenges and offer solutions to the utility industry. Some of our domain solutions are as follows:

- Utilities Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and the billing automation solution
- Advance Metering and Meter Data Management
- Training and Knowledge Management
- Energy Trading, Risk Management and Power Portfolio Management
- Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition-Distribution Management System (SCADA-DMS) or Energy Management System (EMS) and Outage Management Systems (OMS)
- Power Network Management System, Revenue Protections and Energy Auditing
- Integrated Telecommunication Network solutions
- Enterprise Mobility Solutions

4. CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

Tech Mahindra's business success depends upon its ability to foster lasting customer relationships. The company is committed to dealing with the customers fairly, honestly and with integrity. Specifically, the following guidelines should be kept in mind while dealing with the customer. Information supplied to the customers should be accurate and complete to the best of the knowledge. Directors and the Associates should not misrepresent information to customers. Directors and Associates should not refuse to give services to the customers, in the event one of the Tech Mahindra's competitors is also providing services to the same customer. Customers entertainment should not exceed reasonable and customary business practice. Director and Associates should not provide entertainment or other benefits that could be viewed as an inducement to or a reward for, customers purchase decisions. Our products and services shall be technologically competitive and fulfilling the needs of our customers, shall offer the best possible value to our customers such that we become the customers' first choice for quality and service. No false or misleading claims shall be made whilst marketing our product or services.

Our service standards shall be in the highest possible order. Mutually beneficial relationships of an enduring nature will be built with the customers. Our response to the needs and expectation of customers shall be speedy, courteous and effective. Customer complaints and warrantie will be attended to the full satisfaction of the customer.

Key Customers:

- MediaTek
- BlackBerry
- Nokia
- Telus
- Pantech
- Telecom
- Huawei
- htc
- SONY

Stakeholder Relationship Management: We helped leading sports administrators deliver CRM solutions to enhance their relationships with stakeholders. Standalone components of these solutions include:

- Competitor database
- Coach/referee information
- Online AGM registration
- Match and results database
- Online store
- Integration with external systems

5. THE TECH MAHINDRA SOLUTION

SAP APO(Advance Planning and Optimization): SAP SCM is in one of the best repository for all advanced supply chain planning and execution functionalities. We work together with our customers, in their pursuit of improving the Supply chain effectiveness, with the help of SAP SCM – APO tool. We partners with our customers right from the problem definition stage to SAP APO (Advanced Planning & Optimization) implementation and ongoing maintenance and realignment. Today, we are supporting the global corporations in managing their supply chain using SAP. SCM and APO offers 4 modules DP, SNP, PPDS and GATP and is integrated via core interface to SAP ERP. Tech Mahindra has expertise in all these modules.

SAP BPC (Business Planning and consulisation): Today, Finance and Financial Planning & Analysis (FP&A) departments are compelled to have shorter budgeting cycles, improved closing process, full regulatory compliance, more accurate reporting and better and timely decisions.

Tech Mahindra's SAP BPC is an application dedicated to financial processes (Planning, Budgeting & Forecasting and Legal & Management Consolidation) on a unified platform. Owned by the business and designed by the end user, it is the target environment to support planning, consolidation and financial reporting.

SAP FSCM(Financial Supply Chain Management): Eliminate inefficient processes in the financial supply chain management through SAP Financial Supply Chain Management (FSCM). SAP FSCM comprises an integrated set of solutions that supports a broad set of processes affecting work capital management. This approach enables organizations to influence a comprehensive set of levers that can optimize the cash flows, lower working capital requirements and the cost of running the finance and treasury operation

SAP GRC Access & Process Control: Tech Mahindra's services in SAP GRC Access & Process Control help the companies automate the access and authorization management and the overall internal controls management systems

6. SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

Environmental Health & Safety: SAP Environment, Health, and Safety Management solution supports compliance in product safety, dangerous goods management, hazardous substance management, industrial hygiene and safety, occupational health and waste management. The solution also seamlessly integrates with other business processes of materials management, plant maintenance, quality management; sales and distribution. Also, the solution supports compliance to all international regulations in safety, dangerous and hazardous goods management, health and waste management.

Environmental Compliance Solutions: As environmental mandates come into effect, organizations face the difficult task of identifying, managing, tracking and ultimately submitting vast amount of compliance related data and information from multiple sources within an organization. A number of organizations today rely on manual checklists and excel sheets to manage these compliance requirements and run the risk of errors and non-compliance.

Tech Mahindra's environmental compliance solutions provide end to end services starting with domain consulting to system implementation/integration to post implementation support. This will ultimately help organizations streamline and manage relevant information in a systematic way and ultimately help them comply with various mandates.

Green Data Centers: Data Centers today are responsible for approximately 2% of global Green House Gas (GHG) emissions. To add to this, the evolution of cloud based solutions and the ever increasing density of computing equipment is making it necessary for CIOs and IT managers to closely monitor and control their data center energy usage.

To address this market, we have been offering data center management services for nearly two decades. We manage, host and consolidate IT infrastructure as a part of our data center services. We provide end-to-end solutions in Green Data Center implementation and upgrade by offering assessment, design and architecture, implementation and post-implementation support services.

7. TRAINING STRATEGY

Standardization and Training: This helps develop a more efficient business operation through standardization across the organization and sharing of key skills, processes and resources.

Spotlight: Our recent standardization of skills and talent management solution to a global oil and gas major yielded:

- Consistency of business processes
- Skills and information transfer across team, contractors, and business unit (BU) representatives
- Development of maintenance and inspection procedures training
- Improved data quality and equipment reliability
- Creation of the Centre of Excellence for talent management
- Skills consistency and re-usability across assets which increased training and personnel investment ROI

Training Solutions: Backed with a strong people and process base, innovative and learner-centric design, we develop customised training products and solutions to provide customers and their partners with an enriching learning experience. Our key training solutions include:

- On-boarding and competency development to move employees from awareness to skilled to mastery
- Training for Technical Topics, Products, Sales, Software Applications, Soft Skills, Health and Safety, Compliance & Ethics, Operating Procedures
- Training Delivery Through Web, DVDs, Live/Virtual Classroom
- Embracing new technology, such as mobile and social media
- Recruitment & Competency Assessment
- Localisation and Translation
- Development of Online Help and User Manuals

We also provide support services such as creation of technical FAQs, whitepapers, and Web content updates.

8. TECHNOLOGY OFFERINGS

Business Transformation Services: We help to reduce and optimize the Information Technology (IT) spend by effective utilization of application tools. This is achieved through consolidation of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERPs), portfolio rationalization, process standardization and so on.

Our Business Transformation Services include:

- **Consulting**
We help companies leverage IT to execute their business strategies, explore new opportunities, create virtual enterprises, grow competencies and forge closer ties with customers. We help our customers design change and implement solutions across multiple platforms.
- **System Integration**

We provide end-to-end services to enable implementation and integration of products to meet the customer business and IT requirements

- Implementation of products and package, such as ERP and Customer Relationship Management (CRM)
- Integration of products using leading middleware products
- Application and data migration services

Product Engineering Services: Our Product Engineering Services include:

- **New Product Introduction (NPI)**

We partner with our customers to develop new products and we have established ecosystems to support New Product Development activities. The Engineering Services team has expertise across wide spectrum of Product Engineering covering:

- Software Product Development
- Hardware and Software required for Technology Devices and Equipment

- **Product Maintenance**

We collaborate with our customers by taking over their non-core activities in product engineering. We ensure smooth re-badging, transition and integration into our environment, to enable our customers focus more on their core product delivery.

- **Product Testing**

Our product testing services help to test a wide variety of products in a “crowd sourcing model”. We also offer product testing with innovative business models, such as “pay-per-bug” based on the business scenario.

9. COMPETITORS

- **Hexaware:** Hexaware Technologies Limited (HTL) is an information technologies and business method outsourcing service provider company based in Navi Mumbai, India. Hexaware Technologies Limited (HTL) was founded in 1990. The company provides software services for Banking, Financial Services, Capital Markets, Healthcare, Insurance, Manufacturing, Retail, Education, Telecom, Professional services (Tax, Audit, Accounting and Legal), Transportation and Logistics the company specialized in an array of areas encompassing the Application Transformation Management, Enterprise Solutions, Business Intelligence & Analytics, Digital Assurance, Infrastructure Management Services, Digital and Business Process Services.
- **Wipro:** The company was incorporated on 29th Dec 1945 in Amalner, Maharashtra by Mohamed Premji as Western India Vegetable Products Limited, later abbreviated to **Wipro**. On 7 June 1977, the name of the company changed company name Western India Vegetable Products Limited, to Wipro Products Limited
- **Tata Consultancy Services:** Tata Consultancy Services Limited (TCS) is a subsidiary of the Tata Group, an Indian information technology consulting and business solutions company which operates in 46 countries worldwide. TCS Limited was established in 1968 by a division of Tata Sons Limited. Its early contracts included punched card services to TISCO (now Tata Steel), working on an Inter-Branch Reconciliation System for the Central Bank of India. In 1975 TCS

made an electronic depository and trading system called SEMCOM for Swiss company. TCS also established India's first software research and development center called Tata Research Development and Design Centre in Pune, Maharashtra. On 25th Aug 2004, TCS became a Publicly Listed Company.

- **Hindustan Computers Limited(HCL) Technologies:** HCL is an Indian multinational company, headquarter is located at Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India. It is a subsidiary of HCL Enterprise. Originally, the development and research division of HCL(Hindustan Computers Limited), it emerged as an independent company in 1991 when HCL ventured into the software services business.
- **Infosys:** Infosys was established by seven engineers in Pune, India, with an initial capital of \$250 in 1981. It was registered as **Infosys Consultants Private Limited** on 2 Jul 1981. In 1983, Infosys relocated its office to Bengaluru, Karnataka, India. It was later renamed to **Infosys Limited** in June 2015.

10. ANNUAL REPORT (2017-2018)

11. SWOT ANALYSIS

Strengths:

Diverse customer base: Tech Mahindra has strategically positioned itself to target diversified end markets. Tech Mahindra offers IT services for different industries including telecom, banking, manufacturing and financial services etc. Providing the services to such a wide customer base reduces business risks.

Presence in diversified geographies: Tech Mahindra has strategically planned its expansion globally in order to serve diverse geographies. Tech Mahindra's markets include developed markets such as North America and Europe; and emerging markets such as Africa, Asia Pacific. Such a wide spread in terms of geography also reduces business risks and over dependence on concentrated markets.

Broad and balanced services portfolio: Tech Mahindra has a broad and balanced service portfolio. The spectrum of services that Tech Mahindra offers include: telecom and enterprise solutions, IT infrastructure services, Business processing outsourcing (BPO) and enterprise services. With such a wide range of offerings, Tech Mahindra is able to attract a diverse base of customer.

Strategic partnerships: Tech Mahindra has established a partner program through which are specifically designed to develop tools to support technology products. It has partnered with the companies like Google, IBM, Microsoft, SAP and many other companies. Such an established network of partners provides the company with a technological boost which helps it to provide more value to its customers.

Weaknesses:

Lack of Scale: Tech Mahindra competes with giants like Infosys, TCS and Accenture etc. As compared with the peers, Tech Mahindra has the lack of scale. In FY 2015, Tech Mahindra could only generate 1/3rd of the revenue generated by TCS. This puts Tech Mahindra in a position of disadvantage.

Opportunities:

Increasing demand for cloud-based solutions: The Global market for the cloud-based services is expected to show strong growth in the years to come. With improving IT (Information Technology) infrastructure in developed and emerging nations and advancement in technology, cloud-based services are expected to take growth at a CAGR of 19% till 2019. Tech Mahindra has established a market for cloud-based service and is expected to benefit from the increasing demand.

Growing enterprise of mobile marketing: With the increasing of mobile working population and emergence of smartphones, business applications are expected to take over the market for enterprise mobility. The global enterprise of mobility solutions market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 24.7% until the year 2021. Tech Mahindra offers a wide range of enterprise mobility solutions and hence is expected to benefit from the growth in demand.

Big Data: There has been a tremendous growth of Data in the recent years and Big Data has been the primary contributor of the same. Big Data basically helps all the organisations who want to

turn the huge amount of data into insightful information. Tech Mahindra offers several services for Big Data and thus is well positioned to benefit.

Threats:

Intense Competition: Tech Mahindra is present in an ever evolving IT(information Technology) industry which is highly competitive. The company competes with all large scale companies like TCS, Infosys, Wipro, HCL and IBM etc.

A slowdown in IT spending: The IT industries has experienced the slowdown in spending globally which suggests that growth in the industry is sluggish and there are uncertainties in the IT market.

Employee attrition: The IT industries in India faces high attrition rate as there are the high number of opportunities for people in the IT sector and employees generally get attracted towards higher compensation. This increases the company's overall expenditure on hiring and training.

12. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER INNOVATIONS

- Eliminates projects and processes that don't work
- Rethink your high-level business strategy
- Recognize and protect Entrepreneur's
- Collaborate with more technology-related industries and companies.

13. CONCLUSIONS

Tech Mahindra is a leading global systems integrator and business transformation consulting organization, focused primarily on the telecommunications industry. Tech Mahindra expanded its Information Technolgy (IT) portfolio in 2009 by acquiring Satyam Computer Services, which post-acquisition got renamed as Mahindra Satyam. While Mahindra Satyam remained as a distinct entity with an independent listing on the BSE-Sensex and NSE-Nifty, it was envisaged by the Boards of Tech Mahindra and Mahindra Satyam that a merger of both the companies, would be the way to go forward.